

The Development of Community Learning Center ‘Bue Ban’ in Driving the Smart City Policy in Khon Kaen, Thailand

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 16, 2025</p> <p>Accepted: June 16, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Model, Public Participation, Khon Kaen, Smart City Thailand</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15683981</p>	<p><i>This research aims (1) to study the contextual conditions of Khon Kaen Urban Community in driving the policy of Smart City Development; (2) to develop the community learning center: Bue Ban (the Old City Pillar Shrine) based on the public participation in driving the policy. This study was carried out by means of the qualitative and operational research methodology with its tools as in-depth interview, Focus Group Discussion and fieldwork. The data were obtained from 66 participants, chosen by Purposive Sampling, and were interpreted by Descriptive Content Analysis. From the study, the learning model called ‘KIDPU’ has been used to develop the community learning center as a part of a smart city development. The research results lead to the development of learning contents on the history of Khon Kaen, History of Bue Ban cultural arts, culture and traditions in six subjects. Each subject had a QR code that could be electronically scanned by mobile phones to obtain the given information immediately, making it less time to study diverse stories of the city in the age of dramatic change in Thailand.</i></p>

Introduction

According to the Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand in 1997, Thailand has had a policy of decentralization that clearly leads to the participation of the people. Participation is an opportunity for people to participate in initiatives, decision-making, joint practice and share responsibility in various matters, which affects the people themselves (Klein, 1998). It is a cooperation of people, individual or group of people who agree and jointly be responsible for carrying out development and change in the desired direction through a group or organization to achieve the desired change (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). It is an opportunity for individuals to participate in helping one another in thinking, planning, making decisions, working together and taking responsibility in various matters that affect the general public in management to achieve the goals of society. The 20-Year National Strategy (2018-2015) is the first national strategy of Thailand, according to the Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand, conducted for the country to achieve the vision that stated “Thailand is stable, prosperous, sustainable, as a developed country through development according to the philosophy of sufficiency economy” (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2017). The national strategy on human resource and capacity development focuses on developing and upgrading people in all dimensions and ages to be a good, competent, and quality human resource who are ready to drive the country's development forward to its full potential (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020).

Khon Kaen is designated as an important city and the center of the northeastern region (Napraphansuk, 2017), (Ruenpakpoj, Aim-Im-Tham, & Sakolnakorn, 2020), (Kamnuansilpa, Laochankham, Crumpton, & Draper, 2020). As a result, the foundation for systematic and continuous provincial development has been organized in order for it to become a smart city according to the national strategy, development processes on technology, health, art, and Khon Kaen city development plan policy are connected with the design of Khon Kaen City to drive it to be a smart city (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). Therefore, the researchers were interested in researching a learning model for developing a smart city through processes on technology, environment, health, art and design of Khon Kaen city by participation of the people for development of the area supporting unlimited learning of the people in Khon Kaen Province in line with the Khon Kaen City Development Plan (Sudhipongpracha & Dahiya, 2019) that aims to develop the smart city as a learning city in the digital age.

Research Objectives

This qualitative research was conducted with the aims (1) to study the contextual conditions of Khon Kaen Urban Community in driving the policy of Smart City Development; (2) to develop the community learning

center: Bue Ban (the Old City Pillar Shrine) based on the public participation in driving the policy of a smart city.

Research Design

This research is divided into 3 phases:

Phase 1: a study/review/synthesis

In this stage, the participation of the community in driving for Khon Kaen smart city was divided into 3 steps. Step 1 was a study/review/synthesis of the guidelines for community participation in driving for Khon Kaen smart city from documents, concepts, theories and related research. Step 2 was an interview of key informants in the community of Khon Kaen Municipality. Step 3 was an organization of an academic seminar to confirm the information and results obtained from the study/review/synthetic from documents, concepts, theories, related research and interviews.

Phase 2: a development of a learning model

This model was developed through the processes on technology, environment, health, art, and city design in Khon Kaen with community participation, divided into 2 steps. Step 1 was a meeting to review development guidelines. Step 2 was a design of the community learning by representatives from Khon Kaen Municipality, local scholars, community representatives, Khon Kaen Tae Hoop Club, together with the research team.

Phase 3: a development in the area

In this stage, there was the development of the community learning center in the area for people in Khon Kaen Province together with the research team and related agencies.

Results

According to the study of conditions and contexts of participation of Khon Kaen urban community in driving for a smart city, it was found that the community had not yet received full cooperation because the past 3 times of the development in the area around Bue Ban were the development and employment plan and idea from the local government organization, which is now Khon Kaen Municipality, which had allocated a budget for an employment contract, causing no participation of the community around Bue Ban.

For the development of the community learning center of Khon Kaen urban community in driving a smart city, the research was based on the core principles of operational and qualitative research, including planning, execution, observation and reflection of practice results, as well as considering the improvement of the plan to achieve a new operational plan. The synthetic results from the interview, group discussion and academic discussion about community participation in building a smart city could be written as a learning model of participation of the Khon Kaen community in driving for a smart city as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Knowledge Management Model for Creating a Smart City in Khon Kaen

The results from jointly developing a learning model of participation of Khon Kaen urban communities in driving for a smart city revealed that 1) the community worked together to raise awareness of people in the community to love and learn their hometown and to be proud of their community; 2) the community reflected the identity of Khon Kaen people through the tools used in occupation, such as a woven bamboo container for steamed glutinous rice (*Kratip-khow-niew*), yarn weaving tool (*A-gro-dai*), silk weaving tool (*Feuw*), and silkworm. These are the wisdom of ancestors that can be applied to modern innovations for sustainability that leads to a good conscience with the motto “Don't forget the old stuff, don't get addicted on new things.”; 3) the community made decisions on appropriate actions through meeting, group discussion, discussion, and collective agreements by participation of all parties, which led to the development of innovations; 4) the development of creative spaces in the beloved community for religious activities and other activities was conducted by the community selecting the area by themselves. Also, from the research results, it could be synthesized into a learning model called ‘KIDPU’, which included (1) K: Knowledge Management; (2) I: Identity; (3) D: Development; (4) P: Publication and (5) U: Utilization.

Figure 2: A Learning Model of Public Participation in Driving a Smart City, Khon Kaen, Thailand

From this stage of research, it leads to the implications of the research results as follows:

1) Policy implication - Policy implication is the use of policy research as information for the promulgation of the ordinance of Khon Kaen Municipality.

2) Academic implication- It is the use of research results for teaching the history of Khon Kaen Province, which leads to learning about creating learning media about the history of Khon Kaen, History of Bue Ban, as well as good cultural arts, culture and traditions of Khon Kaen Province. Especially, in this research, the research team created a tool containing 6 subjects of knowledge. Each subject had a QR code that could be scanned to show information immediately, making it less time-consuming to research more diverse stories in the age of dramatic change.

3) Public implication - The results of this research were beneficial to people in terms of improving people's quality of life and economy, such as the use of arts and culture, sufficiency economy lifestyle, etc. The research team created innovations as follows; 1) smart electric pole, 2) a sign indicating the direction of Bue Ban, 3) a sign indicating the direction of Bue Ban on the road in the middle of the city at the entrance to Bue Ban, 4) a painted road surface leading to Bue Ban that is a colorful road surface development for a clean and pleasant view for people in the community, 5) landscape improvement of Bue Ban, both inside and outside of the shrine, for a clean and beautiful place, where people can use it for activities, 6) a check-in point that indicates the information of Bue Ban on the Google Maps of Thailand for convenient search for visitors.

4) Spatial utilization- it is the utilization of the research result in at least 6 communities in Khon Kaen Municipality, including Wat That Community, Wat Klang Community, Nong Waeng Community 1, Nong Waeng Community 2, Nong Waeng Community 3, and Nong Waeng Community 4.

5) Indirect utilization- it is the creation of spiritual values, uplifting the mind, creating aesthetics, creating happiness for people in the community.

Discussion

1) A smart city development - The development of a smart city must come from the cooperation of the community from factors that exist within the community combined with the appropriate use of modern technology. The development of read community should start from the Old City Pillar Shrine (Bue Ban), which is the center of the mind of Khon Kaen people. It is an area that people have been paying attention to for a long time, and wanted to develop in parallel with the development of modern technology, where people can easily visit and access to information from the curated knowledge base easily. This is consistent with the study of Wanatham Kanchanasuwan (2010), Strong Community Management Process: Model, Factors and Indicators, which found that there are seven important management processes of managing strong communities in Thai society that contribute to the potential of a strong community development, including (1) the process of community participation, (2) the process of learning exchange, (3) the process of production and restoration, (4) the process of exercising community rights and community ordinances, (5) the process of community decision-making, (6) the process of network development, and (7) the process of self-management. In addition, the issue of study result to create indicators of strong community could be divided into four components, including economic dimension, social and community organization dimension, cultural and learning dimension, and natural resources and environment dimension.

2) Mutual benefit - This research is also an operational research with processes engaging the community and those involved in all activities of the operation to jointly develop the area to support the learning of the community. Therefore, the results of the research are directly beneficial to the community as follows: 2.1) In term of policy utilization - policy utilization is the use of policy research as information for the promulgation of the ordinance of Khon Kaen Municipality. 2.2) Academic utilization is the use of research results for teaching the history of Khon Kaen Province, and lead to learning and creating learning media about the history of Khon Kaen and Bue Ban. 2.3) Public use - The results of this research are beneficial to people in terms of improving people's quality of life and economy, the use of arts and culture, the way of life in a sufficiency economy, etc. 2.4) Spatial utilization is the use of research result in at the specific area of at least six communities in Khon Kaen Municipality. 2.5) Indirect utilization is the creation of spiritual values, uplifting the mind, creating aesthetics, and creating happiness for people in the community- firstly, it is the interaction between government agencies and the research community and the effort to drive and propagate to utilize the research results. The two factors are consistent with Phakpoom Tippakoon (2019), who studied key factors of the utilization of research by government agencies in Thailand. For the researches to be utilized for more policy purposes, the connection mechanism between government and research sectors that allows for mutually exchanging interactions must be built. Currently, some research funding agencies (for example, Thailand Science Research and Innovation) have emphasized the connection between the researcher and the beneficiary throughout the research processes. However, until now, there has not been a systematic assessment of whether the approach is effective in terms of increasing the level of utilization or not. Secondly, motivating researchers to apply their research results for policy utilization should be considered. It can be said that there is currently no concrete incentive system that would attract researchers to put their work for utilization. Although, there are indicators for the research result utilization in terms of education quality assessment in higher education institutions, but such conditions are not motivating at the individual level. Therefore, a new incentive system may need to be designed to allow researchers to see the benefits of investing in driving research result for policy utilization. Thirdly, the agencies' need for utilizing research result is one of the most important factors for the level of utilization. The key point is to know the kind of research needed by government agencies for utilization. At this point, the mechanism connecting for the continuous and regular exchange of information between government agencies and researchers should be able to identify the needs of users and make the research more responsive to their needs and demands.

Suggestions

Suggestion at the policy level

According to the research, it was found that the participation of the Khon Kaen community in driving for a smart city caused by the participation of people within the community through the support of government and private agencies through various activities. Therefore, executives or related parties should encourage and support the development of a learning model based on factors that exist within the community for people in the community to be proud and love of their hometown and to create a learning space within the community.

Suggestions for applying the research results

According to the research results, it was found that the participation of the Khon Kaen community in driving for a smart city made people in the community to love their hometown. Therefore, stakeholders should apply the model from this research to further develop the community as a cultural tourist destination for stability, prosperity and sustainability.

Suggestions for further research

- 1) There should be a study on the development of cultural tourism areas for sustainability in the community based on government policies.
- 2) There should be a study on the factors affecting the success of cultural tourism in terms of both administration and management based on cooperation of all relevant sectors.

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